

Kinetics and Mechanism of Osmium(VIII)-catalysed Oxidation of Selenium(IV) by Periodate

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Manuscript received 18 September 1989, revised 7 February 1990, accepted 28 February 1990

The reaction is first order in oxidant and catalyst and zero order in substrate. The rate decreases with increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ and increases with increase in ionic strength. E_a and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are found to be $47.9 \pm 0.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-33.0 \pm 1.8 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. A suitable mechanism is proposed.

RECENTLY we have reported the mechanism of oxidation of selenium(IV) by periodate in acid as well as in alkaline medium¹. We observed that Ru^{III} exerts a profound catalytic effect on this reaction in acid medium while Os^{VIII} has a similar effect in alkaline medium. The mechanism of the Ru^{III} catalysis has been found to be the same as the one already reported², wherein Ru^{VIII} is the reactive species. We now report the kinetics and mechanism of Os^{VIII} catalysed oxidation of Se^{IV} by periodate in alkaline medium. In this reaction Os^{VIII} has been found to be the reactive species and the rate-determining step involves interaction between Os^{VI} and periodate.

Experimental

An aqueous solution of selenite was prepared from sodium selenite (B.D.H., L.R.) and its strength determined³. Aqueous solutions of periodate, selenate and iodate were prepared from BDH, AR grade sodium metaperiodate, sodium selenate and potassium iodate (all AnalaR) respectively. An aqueous solution of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ Os^{VIII} was prepared by dissolving OsO_4 (Johnson Mathey) in 0.5 M sodium hydroxide and standardised⁴. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade.

The kinetics of the reaction were studied in $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ alkali at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, under the condition $[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}] \gg [\text{periodate}] \gg [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$. The reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically following the absorbance of periodate at 280 nm where it had considerable absorbance, and all other ions involved had negligible absorbance. The pseudo-first order rate constants were found to be reproducible within $\pm 5\%$.

In order to determine the stoichiometry of the reaction, two to four-fold excess of periodate was allowed to react with a known concentration of Se^{IV} at 25° in presence of $5.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$ Os^{VIII} in 0.1 M alkali. After completion of the reaction,

the concentration of the unreacted oxidant was determined spectrophotometrically. The stoichiometry was found to correspond to the mole ratio of 1 : 1.

Results and Discussion

The order with respect to periodate was determined in 0.1 M alkali keeping $[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]$ constant and varying $[\text{periodate}]$ from 5.0×10^{-4} to $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$. The plots of $\log [\text{periodate}]$ vs time were found to be linear beyond two half-lives of the reaction, indicating first order dependence on $[\text{periodate}]$. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was found to be invariant with $[\text{periodate}]$ confirming first order with respect to periodate (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - VARIATION OF k_{obs} WITH $[\text{PERIODATE}]$ AND $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$

$[\text{OH}^-] = 0.1 \text{ M}$, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$, $\text{Temp.} = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

$[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]$ $\times 10^3 \text{ M}$	$[\text{per}]$ $\times 10^4 \text{ M}$	$[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ $\times 10^7 \text{ M}$	k_{obs} $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
3.0	5.0	5.0	6.2
3.0	10.0	5.0	6.4
3.0	15.0	5.0	6.3
3.0	20.0	5.0	6.2
3.0	25.0	5.0	6.3
2.0	10.0	1.0	1.2
2.0	10.0	2.0	2.7
2.0	10.0	4.0	5.6
2.0	10.0	6.0	8.3
2.0	10.0	8.0	10.9
2.0	10.0	10.0	13.3
2.0	10.0	12.0	17.8
2.0	10.0	15.0	21.9

The rate of the reaction was found to increase with increase in $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$. A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ was found to be a straight line with unit slope, indicating the order with respect to Os^{VIII} .

to be unity. The rate of reaction was found to be independent of $[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]$ in the range of 0.01–0.1M, indicating zero order dependence on $[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}]$. Increase in $[\text{OH}^-]$ was found to retard the reaction while increase in ionic strength (adjusted with sodium perchlorate) was found to cause acceleration (Table 2). Even 20-fold excess of the products of the reaction, selenate and iodate, were found not to have any effect on the rate. The reaction was found to obey Arrhenius temperature dependence; the pseudo-first order rate constants at 25, 30, 35 and 40° being 6.0×10^{-4} , 8.2×10^{-4} , 1.1×10^{-3} and $1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The activation parameters E_a and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ at 25° computed by the method of linear least-squares, were $47.9 \pm 0.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-33.0 \pm 1.8 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[\text{OH}^-]$ AND IONIC STRENGTH (μ) ON k_{obs}

$[\text{Se}^{\text{IV}}] = 0.02 \text{ M}$, $[\text{per}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$,

$[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$, Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

$[\text{OH}^-]$ $\times 10 \text{ M}$	μ $\times 10 \text{ M}$	k_{obs} $\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$
1.0	10.0	6.3
2.0	10.0	5.1
4.0	10.0	3.9
6.0	10.0	3.5
8.0	10.0	3.3
10.0	10.0	3.1
1.0	1.6	3.2
1.0	2.0	3.6
1.0	4.0	4.7
1.0	6.0	5.5
1.0	8.0	5.9

In 0.1–1.0M aqueous alkaline medium employed in the present investigation, Se^{IV} exists⁶ as SeO_3^{2-} and periodate exists as an equilibrium mixture of the species^{6–8} $\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{2-}$ and $\text{H}_3\text{IO}_6^{3-}$. In aqueous solutions Os^{VIII} exists⁹ as OsO_4 , $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^-$ and $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$. In alkaline solutions the latter two species are known to be present in equilibrium,

the equilibrium constant, K at 25° being 24 ± 4 (Ref. 8). In many of the oxidations involving Os^{VIII} as catalyst the order with respect to alkali is observed to tend to zero above 0.1M alkali^{10,11} indicating shift of equilibrium (1) towards complete formation of $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$. Under the present experimental conditions, Os^{VIII} may therefore be presumed to exist almost exclusively as $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$. In aqueous solutions although Os^{VI} exists⁹ as OsO_3 and $[\text{OsO}_2(\text{OH})_4]^{2-}$, the latter is known to be the reduction product¹² of $[\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2]^{2-}$. In the present investigation, since Os^{VI} is derived from Os^{VIII} , it may be expected that

Os^{VI} is present as $[\text{OsO}_2(\text{OH})_4]^{2-}$. When Os^{VIII} solutions are mixed with a solution of Se^{IV} in 0.1 to 1.0M alkali, a pale pink colour is obtained, the spectrum of which is found to coincide¹³ with that of $[\text{OsO}_2(\text{OH})_4]^{2-}$ indicating the Os^{VI} species involved in the present investigation to be $[\text{OsO}_2(\text{OH})_4]^{2-}$.

On the basis of our experimental observations, the following mechanism has been proposed:

This mechanism leads to the rate expression,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{per}]_t}{dt} = \frac{[\text{per}]_t[\text{Os}^{\text{VI}}][k_1 + k_2K[\text{OH}^-]]}{[1 + K[\text{OH}^-]]} \quad (6)$$

where $[\text{per}]_t = [\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{2-}] + [\text{H}_2\text{IO}_6^{3-}]$ and $K = K'/K_w$, where K' is the third dissociation constant of periodic acid and K_w the ionic product of water. Since Os^{VI} is formed from Os^{VIII} in a fast step and since the concentration of the latter is very small compared to that of Se^{IV} , the concentration of Os^{VI} may be taken to be the same as that of Os^{VIII} . Hence equation (6) may be written as

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{per}]_t}{dt} = \frac{[\text{per}]_t[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][k_1 + k_2K[\text{OH}^-]]}{[1 + K[\text{OH}^-]]} \quad (7)$$

k_{obs} may, therefore, be given as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][k_1 + k_2K[\text{OH}^-]]}{[1 + K[\text{OH}^-]]} \quad (8)$$

Rearranging equation (8),

$$k_{\text{obs}}[1 + K[\text{OH}^-]] = [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}][k_1 + k_2[\text{OH}^-]] \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) indicates that the plot of $k_{\text{obs}}[1 + K[\text{OH}^-]]$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ should be a straight line with an intercept corresponding to $k_1[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ and slope corresponding to $k_2K[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$. The expected curve was obtained when the data in Table 2 were plotted (Fig. 1), thus supporting the proposed mechanism. The third dissociation constant of periodic acid (K') has been reported to be 6.3×10^{-13} at 25°⁷. The value of K is therefore 62.6 at 25°. From this value of K and the slope and intercept of Fig. 1, the values of k_1 and k_2 were computed to be 6.7×10^3 and $5.3 \times 10^3 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively.

Fig. 1. Plot of $k_{obs} [1 + K[OH^-]]$ vs $[OH^-]$.

It may, therefore, be seen that the decrease in rate with increase in $[OH^-]$ is due to the conversion of $H_3IO_3^{2-}$ into less electrophilic $H_2IO_3^{3-}$ species.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (N.S. and R.R.) are grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Research Fellowships.

References

1. N. SRIDEVI, R. RAMBABU P. VANI and L. S. A. DIKSHITULU *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, 29, 63.
2. L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, P. VANI and V. H. RAO, *Inorg Nucl. Chem. Lett.*, 1981, 17, 187.
3. S. BARBAS and W. C. COOPER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 129.
4. F. E. BEAMISH, "The Analytical Chemistry of Noble Metals", Pergamon, London, 1966, p. 326.
5. L. BARCZA and L. G. SILLEN, *Acta Chem. Scand*, 1971, 25, 1250.
6. C. E. CROUTHAMEL, H. V. MEEK, D. S. MARTIN and C. V. BANKS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3031; H. C. MISHRA and M. C. R. SYMONS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1194; E. E. MERCER and D. J. FARRAR, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1968, 46, 2679.
7. G. J. BUIST, W. C. P. HIPPERSON and J. D. LEWIS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 307.
8. R. M. KREN and H. W. DODGEN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 446; V. J. SHINER and C. R. WASMUTH *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 81, 37.
9. W. P. GRIFFITH, *Quart. Rev.*, 1965, 19, 259.
10. D. MOHAN and Y. K. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1085.
11. N. P. SINGH, V. N. SINGH and M. P. SINGH, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1968, 21, 2913; N. P. SINGH, V. N. SINGH, H. S. SINGH and M. P. SINGH, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1970, 23, 921; V. LAL, V. N. SINGH, H. S. SINGH and M. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 392.
12. N. N. GREENWOOD and A. EARNEHAW, "Chemistry of the Elements", Pergamon, New York, 1984, p. 1257.
13. K. A. LOTT and M. C. R. SYMONS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 973.